

Variations in Political Trolling Tactics Towards Democrats and Republican Candidates Between two US Presidential Election Cycles

Fichman, Pnina RKCSI, Indiana University, Bloomington USA | fichman@indiana.edu
Akter, Shohana RKCSI, Indiana University, Bloomington USA | sakter@iu.edu
Rathi, Maanvi RKCSI, Indiana University, Bloomington USA | mrathi@iu.edu
Tess, Rutherford RKCSI, Indiana University, Bloomington USA | teruther@iu.edu
Lilly, Dolliff RKCSI, Indiana University, Bloomington USA | ldolliff@iu.edu

ABSTRACT

Major efforts have been made to combat disinformation and trolling on Twitter, due to their impact on election results across the globe. Even so, trolling seems to be as prevalent as ever before. We aim to examine if and how the extent of trolling toward political figures on Twitter changed between the 2016 and 2020 US presidential election cycles by analyzing outrage comments made towards tweets by a total of 20 Democrat and Republican candidates for President/VP and Senate/House. Based on content analysis of 9,461 comments, we found significantly more trolling towards Republicans than Democrats, demonstrating trolling asymmetry. We also found that between 2016 and 2020, there was a significant increase in overall trolling towards Republicans, but not in overall trolling towards President/VP candidates, highlighting a more obvious increase in domestic trolling than that of the external interference in election results.

KEYWORDS

Political trolling, Trolling asymmetry, Twitter

INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

“Trolling is an umbrella term for a spectrum of multidimensional, antagonistic, antisocial, or deviant behaviors and motivations online, [involving any] behavior intended to provoke a reaction in another user” (Ortiz, 2020, p. 1), varying across different online communities and platforms (Sanfillipo et al., 2017). However, online trolling includes not only antisocial online behavior (Cruz et al., 2018), but also political and ideological trolling (Sanfillipo et al., 2017) that often involve political satire (Fichman, 2020) and humor (Sanfillipo et al., 2017). Moreover, trolling commonly refers to state-sponsored trolling such as the Russian troll farms (Zalenkauskaitė & Niezgodą, 2017) and the IRA involvement in the US presidential elections (Kim, et al., 2019). Trolling often leads to mis/disinformation (Fichman & Vaughn, 2021; Norri-Sederholm, 2020), intensified political polarization (Bulut & Yörük, 2017), and, in extreme cases, victim suicide (Coles & West, 2016). The act of studying political trolling has become increasingly critical, as political discussion online has grown in recent years, and political digital ad spending per year has increased from 1.79 billion dollars in 2018 to 2.84 billion dollars in 2019 (Dixon, 2022).

While social media may be an “important outlet for political expression” (Asenas & Hubble, 2018, p. 37), the platforms do not always foster civil discourse necessary to support democracy, and instead they enable toxic disinhibition (Suler, 2004) and permit posts with a range of outrage tactics (Sobieraj & Berry, 2011). Political trolling includes baiting opponents into conflict (Flores-Saviaga et al., 2018) and provoking outrage (Lieback, 2019; Sobieraj & Berry, 2011) to increase the divide between different sides of the political spectrum (Fichman & Rathi, 2022). Social media plays a major role in sharing and disseminating trolling activities either as political bigshots (Brady, et.al., 2019) or politically engaged individuals (Dvir-Gvirsman et al., 2022; Murdani et al., 2022). There was a significant increase in efforts to develop sociotechnical mechanisms between the 2016 and 2020 election cycles to combat trolling and the spread of disinformation. “Though the 2020 presidential election was not marked by substantial bot activity or foreign interference, Trump-supporting accounts and media outlets appear to have engaged in the promotion of a “disinformation campaign” ... full of false, misleading, or unverifiable claims about voting fraud” (Kennedy et al., 2022, p.5), creating a dire need to conduct a longitudinal study of trolling. Our study focuses on the nature and prevalence of political trolling on Twitter during two US presidential election cycles (2016 & 2020).

In addition to the possible change between these two elections, we can expect to find differences in trolling toward Democrats and Republicans because there is evidence showing differences between Democrats and Republicans, not only in the use of social media platforms, but also in the extent that they view, redistribute, and believe in disinformation and fake news (e.g., Freelon, Marwick, & Kreiss, 2020; Grinberg et al., 2019; Garimella, & Weber, 2017; Grossmann & Hopkins, 2019; Linvill & Warren, 2021). The difference in trolling toward Republicans and Democrats is particularly expected because trolling and disinformation feed off of each other (Fichman & Vaughn, 2021), but it is still unclear if the differences in their nature will persist, increase, decrease, or change over time. In fact, “American politics has often been an arena for angry minds” (Hofstadter, 2012, p.77), and is also not symmetrical in its nature. While Republicans work on their abstract ideological beliefs, Democrats aim at achieving collective interests (Grossmann, & Hopkins, 2016). Still, both utilize social media to engage with the public (e.g., Brady, et.al., 2019; Dvir-Gvirzman, et. Al., 2022; Murdani, Haqqi, & Alchatib, 2022). Furthermore, political polarization was also documented in online hashtag activism (Van der Linden, et.al, 2021). And while “hashtag activism captures headlines, conservative digital activism is proving more effective on the ground” (Schradie, 2019). Indeed, scholars found support for the “amplification of the right thesis”, for example, by providing evidence that right-leaning sources gain more visibility on social media (González-Bailón et al., 2022). This digital activism gap (Schradie, 2019) may also be visible in the extent and style of trolling.

Our study examines not only the variations in trolling over time, but also the variations in trolling between Republicans and Democrats, addressing the question: How did trolling towards Republicans and Democrats (President/ VP and House/Senate candidates) on Twitter change between two US presidential election cycles (2016 and 2020)?

METHOD

To address the research question, we chose to collect data from Twitter because the platform has become the breeding ground for political trolling; “a study of 134,000 offensive social media posts found that 88% of these posts occur on Twitter” (Case & King, 2018, p. 2). Using ExportComments.com, we collected the data from both election cycles, from 20 politician accounts from both parties, Democrats and Republicans, including the President and Vice President candidate accounts, as well as those of the candidates for the House and Senate from both parties. Because Trump, Pence, and Pelosi were included in both elections, the 20 accounts include 17 individuals (Table 1). The sample in each election included the most recent tweets leading to the election date in that election cycle. Specifically, the sample data for the 2016 election cycle includes the 20 tweets that the ten politicians posted on, or prior to, November 8, 2016, and the sample data for the 2020 election cycle includes the 20 tweets that the 10 politicians posted on, or prior to, November 3, 2020. Thus, we sampled 400 tweets (20 tweets from 20 accounts) and 9,461 comments (25 comments per tweet when possible; two accounts, Duckworth and Schumer, had fewer than 25 comments per tweet).

	2016	Party	Post	2020	Party	Post
President/ VP	Hillary Clinton	D	President	Joe Biden	D	President
	Donald Trump	R	President	Donald Trump	R	President
	Tim Kaine	D	VP	Kamala Harris	D	VP
	Mike Pence	R	VP	Mike Pence	R	VP
House/ Senate	Tammy Duckworth	D	IL Senate	Ilhan Omar	D	NY Rep
	Nancy Pelosi	D	CA Rep	Alexandria Ocasio-Cortez	D	NY Rep
	Chuck Schumer	D	NY Senate	Nancy Pelosi	D	CA Rep
	Paul Ryan	R	WI Rep	Lindsey Graham	R	SC Senate
	Marco Rubio	R	FL Senate	Mitch McConnell	R	KY Senate
	John McCain	R	AZ Senate	Susan Collins	R	ME Senate

Table 1. Candidates’ Twitter accounts.

Then, we analyzed each of the 9,461 comments by coding the data at the level of an individual comment, using a codebook with four trolling outrage tactics that are common in online political discussions (Sobieraj & Berry, 2011) and have been used later in research on trolling (e.g., Fichman & Rathi, 2022): Derailment, Ideological Misalignment, Insulting and Provocation (Table 2). Two coders coded the comments, and inter-rater reliability was high at 87.8% simple agreement. This was followed by cross-tabulation analysis.

Code	Description	Example
Derailment	Purposefully leading a conversation off track.	“The pandemic saved my marriage, who cares about the poverty rates”
Ideological Misalignment	Comments made because of a difference in political opinions.	“I think that the vaccines should be illegal, my body my choice.”
Insulting	Statements meant to insult an individual or group of people, including name calling and personal attacks.	“She’s so stupid that four years ago she was mixing drinks”
Provocation	Statements intended to elicit a specific reaction.	“VACCINATED WITH WHAT, IS THE MYSTERY!???”

Table 2. Codebook.

FINDINGS & DISCUSSIONS

We examined if the extent of trolling varied depending on political affiliation (Republicans vs. Democrats) and between the two election cycles (2016 & 2020) both for presidential and House/Senate candidates. We summarize the results of the content analysis of comments in Table 3, showing trolling frequencies per code by election and party. This is followed by the Chi-square results of the difference between parties and by election cycle in Table 4.

Tactics	Position	Election Cycle		Party						
				Democrats			Republicans			Total
		2016	2020	2016	2020	Total	2016	2020	Total	
Derailment	President/VP	702	594	371	256	627	331	338	669	1296
	House/Senate	553	568	202	286	488	351	282	633	1121
Ideological Misalign	President/VP	699	675	361	227	588	338	448	786	1374
	House/Senate	223	339	59	225	284	164	114	278	562
Insulting	President/VP	912	870	478	274	752	434	596	1030	1782
	House/Senate	534	1216	188	424	612	346	792	1138	1750
Provocation	President/VP	884	831	460	285	745	424	546	970	1715
	House/Senate	1120	721	443	433	876	677	288	965	1715
Total	President/VP	3197	2970	1670	1042	2712	1527	1928	3455	6167
	House/Senate	2430	2844	892	1368	2260	1538	1476	3014	5274

Table 3. Code frequency.

χ^2	Position	Total Trolling	Derailment	Ideological Misalignment	Insulting	Provocation
Party	President/VP	13.46**	12.91***	1.00	3.20	0.27
	House/Senate	74.95***	0.26	15.15***	66.41***	25.85***
Election	President/VP	3.69	3.55*	0.66	0.43	0.08
	House/Senate	346.03***	6.07**	10.35***	255.24***	248.03***
Democrats by election	President/VP	2.80	1.99	0.01	1.73	0.01
	House/Senate	107.10***	0.94	47.51***	26.89***	73.79***
Republicans by election	President/VP	9.88**	9.37**	0.58	2.52	0.12
	House/Senate	346.98***	6.26**	7.77**	311.21***	207.80***
2016 election by party	President/VP	0.22	0.13	0.12	0.02	0.02
	House/Senate	14.51***	0	7.02**	0.42	4.58*
2020 election by party	President/VP	22.52***	20.93***	0.81	6.96**	0.31
	House/Senate	173.05***	0.74	26.70***	77.33***	28.69***

Sig. (*<.05; **<.01; ***<.001)

Table 4. Chi-square results.

We found that from 2016 to 2020 the extent of trolling towards presidential candidates slightly decreased (3197 vs. 2970 respectively), whereas it significantly increased for the other candidates (2430 vs. 2844 respectively). Even

though Republican presidential candidates were trolled significantly more than Democrats both overall (3455 vs. 2712 respectively) and in the 2020 election cycle (1928 vs. 1042 respectively), they were trolled slightly less than Democrats in 2016 (1527 vs. 1670 respectively). This might be partially explained by the shift in power between the parties during the election; trolls are more likely to target those in position of power (Fichman & Rathi, 2022); Democrats were in power (President Obama) going into the election in 2016, but Republicans held the power (President Trump) going into the 2020 election cycle. Indeed, power dynamic plays an important role in trolling: popular people tend to be more frequently the targets of online trolls (Fichman & Rathi, 2022). This is further demonstrated by the higher trolling towards President/VP candidates compared to Senate/House candidates (6127 vs. 5274 respectively).

We argue that our findings demonstrate political trolling asymmetry, which is very likely triggered by the ideological asymmetry that characterizes American politics. Online trolling asymmetry echoes the partisan asymmetry in digital activism, misinformation, and conspiratorial thinking, to name a few (González-Bailón et al., 2022; Rao et al. 2022; Van der Linden et al., 2021). The trolling asymmetry is evident not only in the extent of trolling in tweets by political candidates, but also in the variations in trolling style (differences in the extent of specific trolling tactics used in tweets by candidates from both sides of the aisle). Indeed, we found significant variations between Republican and Democrat candidates for Senate/House in the extent of most of ideological misalignment, insulting, and provocation tactics: Republicans used each tactic more often than did Democrats (Table 3).

While some users troll politicians with whose ideologies they don't agree (e.g., Democrats trolling Republican candidates), many users troll candidates from their own side to "discipline" or help shape their direction, just as they would troll their own media outlets (Al-Rawi et al., 2021). Indeed, even though most individuals on Twitter interact with those who share their political views, scholars found that "politically motivated individuals provoke interaction by injecting partisan content into information streams whose primary audience consists of ideologically-opposed users" (Conover et al., 2021, p.89). Still, Barbera et al (2015, p.1531) argue that "while evidence [has shown] that liberals were more likely than conservatives to engage in cross-ideological [interactions,...] previous work may have overestimated the degree of ideological segregation in social-media usage"; yet it is possible that Republicans were the target of more trolling overall because in the US, Democrats are more likely to use Twitter than Republicans (Vogel et al., 2021). Whether it is Republicans or Democrats that troll the Republican candidates more, the fact is that Republican candidates were trolled more often than their Democrat counterparts.

CONCLUSION

The sociotechnical affordances of social media platforms enable the wide spread of political trolling and promote disinformation that influences election results. Our study is the first to explore, identify, and begin the discussion of these variations in political trolling, over time and across political affiliation lines. We have made two significant contributions to research on political trolling by providing initial evidence 1) of trolling asymmetry and 2) of the variations in trolling over time. Similar to the digital activism gap that is driven by partisan divide in American politics, we found differences between party lines, in the extent and style of trolling. Specifically, by examining the extent of trolling towards Democrats and Republicans during two election cycles, we identified significant differences based on candidates' political affiliations overall and in each election cycle, and significant variations of trolling over time.

However, the differences we identified might be a result of the limitations of the study, which only provides snapshots of data from two election cycles and is based only on an analysis of 20 Twitter accounts of politicians. It is possible that a bigger sample of accounts or a longer period might provide a modified picture. Still, the benefits and contribution of thematic content analysis to trolling research justifies the sample size, and the snapshots of political trolling include important major political events. Future research may expand the sample to affirm or refute the existence of trolling asymmetry. Another limitation of our study is that we only examined trolling on Twitter, but when trolls target specific political events, they are active on several platforms at once (Howard et. al., 2018), and may use them differently. Thus, it is possible that similar differences may or may not be evident on other sociotechnical platforms. Furthermore, the rise that we found in political trolling between the two election cycles might mostly involve domestic trolling, while the foreign interferences from the IRA accounts declined from the year 2016 to 2020. Future research may further focus on the differences between foreign and domestic trolling to discern the influence of global trolling in national politics from domestic trolling.

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